

BRAND GUIDELINES

Decido

evidence and Cloud for more Informed and effective policies

“ A visual language that combines the advanced “good design” with the innovation of technology, data and emergency. ”

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Logo & brandmark specifications

LOGGO

Logo introduction

Concept

A logo that is a combination of a legible and easy typography with its hi-tech supports: the decido data composition on top and its mark on the side.

The concept that stands behind decido's logotype is the fluid exchange of data together with the idea of community. Each node can either be seen as data or a person.

More in general the concept that support decido is the one of togetherness for greater achievements.

Shape

The shapes send the viewer to a general idea of fluidity, community and technology, all combined together into a simple set of combination that define Decido.

Symbol / Mark

Logo

Decido

Typography

Decido

Logo construction & clear space

Description of the work

Decido's logotype is composed by the IBM plex sans composition of "DECIDO" underneath the same word written with a composition of decido nodes to form the name of the project. This last composition is voluntarily less legible with the goal of transmitting the idea of network and community that is at the base of the visual identity.

The dots are connected through two small arcs of the same radius and the characters of the main font for the logotype have been slightly modified with the aim of providing a more pleasing structure when seen on big dimensions.

As for the respect area the Decido logo must always have a clear space around that is equivalent to the width of the capital "D" of the logo.

Logo colors, application on backgrounds and wrong usages

Background

On darker backgrounds the main colors to be used are “Decido Green” and “Decido Violet”. On clearer or white backgrounds the main choice should always be the dark blue variation. The contrast achieved by these combinations will make the type stand out and be always recognizable among others. In no occasions these combinations have to be altered or changed.

Logo minimum sizes

Logotype

The logotype's minimum size should never be less than 30mm x 10mm.

Marks

The marks' minimum sizes are supposed to be no less than 15mm x 15mm and 8mm x 12mm respectively.

02

**Corporate font &
secondary font**

FONT

Corporate font

IBM Plex sans

Font

A linear font that alone is able to tell the story of humans' relationship with technology and machines, IBM Plex is the main character set for Decido h2020. The font choice is also due to the existence of its counterpart: IBM Plex Mono that, being a monospaced font can be easily read by everyone in specific occasions, making a text more accessible when needed.

Aa IBM plex sans Bold
abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890?!*+(.,)

Aa IBM Plex sans regular
abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890?!*+(.,)

Aa IBM Plex sans Extralight
abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890?!*+(.,)

Aa IBM Plex sans *Italic*
abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890?!+(.,)*

Aa IBM Plex sans Semibold
abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890?!*+(.,)

Secondary font

Source serif

Aa Source serif PRO Bold
abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890?!*+(.,)

Aa Source serif PRO Regular
abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890?!*+(.,)

Aa Source serif PRO Italic
abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890?!+(.,)*

Aa Source serif PRO Light
abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890?!*+(.,)

Aa Source serif PRO Light Italic
abcdefghijklmnopqrstvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890?!+(.,)*

Charaters overview 20pt

1. **The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog**
 2. **The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog**
 3. The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog
 4. *The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog*
 5. The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog
-

1. **The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog**
 2. The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog
 3. *The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog*
 4. The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog
 5. *The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog*
-

Legibility and body text examples

Title 13 / 15,6 (auto) **IBM Plex Sans Bold**

Body text 10 / 12
Source Serif PRO regular

Title 11 / 13,2 (auto) **IBM Plex Sans Semibold**

Body text 9 / 11
IBM Plex Sans Regular

Heading title

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam.

Heading title

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam.

03

Color system: codes and opacity

COLO-

RS

The color system

Dark blue

HEX: 0d0d4c

CMYK: 100; 95; 39; 42

RGB: 13; 13; 76

Opactiy levels: 100%; 80%; 60%; 40%; 20%

Decido Green

HEX: 00ffa3

CMYK: 61; 0; 58; 0

RGB: 0; 255; 163

Opactiy levels: 100%; 80%; 60%; 40%; 20%

Decido Violet

HEX: 7600ff

CMYK: 81; 80; 0; 0

RGB: 118; 0; 255

Opactiy levels: 100%; 80%; 60%; 40%; 20%

logo and brandmark's color system and usages

P.A.L.E.

T.T.E.

Logo color system

Colors

Decido colors are bright and digital and they mean to reflect the nature of the project as much as the era the project is being developed.

The simple palette of only three colors offers endless possibilities and mixtures that will help strengthening the identity of Decido. The colors can be used in the following compositions for both the logo itself and the mark

05

Image treatment of Decido

IMA-

GERY

The color system and the images

Secondary color system

Decido colors are also meant to be used over images in gradients to help the project's identity pop out when needed. The following examples explain the possible compositions and gradients that can be used as stand alones or as simple overlays on images and videos.

In the following pages are displayed a few examples that underlines the usage of the palette on photographs and vector graphics combinations.

Blending modes for images

Blue and violet and Blue/green/violet combinations

Blending modes for images

Blue and green combinations

006

**Additional marks
& graphics**

ADD -

ONS

The decido bubbles & the decido “fingerprint”

Usages

Decido’s interlocking bubbles of data and people offer infinite possible combinations of usages for stationery, image treatments, typography add ons and so on, as long as the bridge between the dots is visible and respects the original grid and color palette it can be a powerful tool at everyone’s use.

Contacts & project partners

CON-
TACTS

Contacts

Contacts

PROJECT PARTNERS

101004605 – DECIDO – H2020 - SC6 - GOVERNANCE -
2018 - 2019 - 2020 / H2020 - SC6 - GOVERNANCE-2020

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